

LINGUODIDACTICS AND MAIN LEARNING CATEGORIES OF LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION: Language education – the process and practice of teaching a second or foreign language – is primarily a branch of applied linguistics, but can be an interdisciplinary field. There are four main learning categories for language education: communicative competencies, proficiencies, cross-cultural experiences, and multiple literacies. The subjects of the linguodidactics study program take into account current trends in linguodidactic research, theory and practice, focusing mainly on the methodology of linguistic research. They are linked to the subjects of the second stage of the university study program teaching academic subjects. The content of the courses takes into account the required content. This article scientifically explains linguodidactics and the role of the linguodidactics in teaching foreign language learners. It also reveals that the four main learning categories of linguodidactics, which are communicative competencies, proficiencies, cross-cultural experiences, and multiple literacies and the way these four categories help learners in their learning foreign languages.

KEY WORDS: linguodidactics, communicative competencies, language proficiencies, cross-cultural experiences, multiple literacies

ЛИНГВОДИДАКТИКА И ОСНОВНЫЕ УЧЕБНЫЕ КАТЕГОРИИ ЯЗЫКОВОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

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АННОТАЦИЯ: Языковое образование — процесс и практика обучения второму или иностранному языку — в первую очередь является отраслью прикладной лингвистики, но может быть и междисциплинарной областью. Существует четыре основных категории обучения для языкового образования: коммуникативные компетенции, навыки, межкультурный опыт и множественная грамотность. Предметы учебной программы по лингводидактике учитывают современные тенденции в лингводидактических исследованиях, теории и практике, уделяя особое внимание методологии лингвистических исследований. Они связаны с предметами второй ступени университетской учебной программы по академическим предметам. Содержание курсов учитывает необходимое содержание. В данной статье научно объясняется лингводидактика и роль лингводидактики в обучении изучающих иностранный язык. Он также показывает, что четыре основные категории обучения лингводидактики, а именно коммуникативные компетенции, навыки, межкультурный опыт и множественная грамотность, и то, как эти четыре категории помогают учащимся в изучении иностранных языков.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: лингводидактика, коммуникативные компетенции, языковые навыки, межкультурный опыт, множественная грамотность.

LINGVODIDAKTIKA VA TIL TA'LIMINING ASOSIY TA'LIM KATEGORIYALARI.

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ANNOTATSIYA: Til ta'limi - ikkinchi yoki chet tilini o'rgatish jarayoni va amaliyoti - birinchi navbatda amaliy tilshunoslikning bir bo'limi, ammo fanlararo soha bo'lishi mumkin. Til ta'limi uchun to'rtta asosiy o'rganish toifasi mavjud: kommunikativ kompetensiyalar, malakalar, madaniyatlararo tajriba va ko'p savodxonlik. Lingvodidaktika o'quv dasturining predmetlari lingvodidaktik tadqiqotlar, nazariya va amaliyotning hozirgi tendentsiyalarini hisobga oladi, asosan lingvistik tadqiqotlar metodologiyasiga e'tibor beradi. Ular o'quv fanlarini o'rgatuvchi universitet o'quv dasturining ikkinchi bosqichidagi fanlar bilan bog'langan. Kurslarning mazmuni talab qilinadigan tarkibni hisobga oladi. Ushbu maqolada lingvodidaktika va lingvodidaktikaning chet tilini o'rganuvchilarga o'rgatishdagi o'zini ilmiy jihatdan tushuntiriladi. Shuningdek, u kommunikativ kompetensiyalar, malakalar, madaniyatlararo tajriba va ko'p savodxonlik bo'lgan lingvodidaktikaning to'rtta asosiy o'quv toifalari va bu to'rtta toifa o'quvchilarga chet tillarini o'rganishda yordam berish usullarini ochib beradi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: lingvodidaktika, kommunikativ kompetensiyalar, til bilimlari, madaniyatlararo tajriba, ko'p savodxonlik

INTRODUCTION

Languages are regarded as attractive according to the economic power or cultural values and prestige attributed to them by the mainstream of a society, which tends to privilege national or international languages. The resolution of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improvement to the study of foreign languages" puts a great challenge for everyone who wish to learn a foreign language.[1]

One of the tasks of teaching a foreign language is to establish communication skills, which is impossible without studying linguodidactics that is a deep knowledge of the language theory. Under the terms of teaching linguodidactics appears as a supportive unit of the transmitted content.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Linguodidactics – a scientific discipline and language education, which is rising its origins in the 1970th years. Since these years, teaching languages aims to strengthen its theoretical foundations through the implementation of a truly integrative approach to the identification of main regularities of the pedagogical process of teaching foreign languages in order to create an objective scientific basis for evaluating the effectiveness of teaching methods and their further improvement.

Language education – the process and practice of teaching a second or foreign language is primarily a branch of applied linguistics, but can be an interdisciplinary field. There are four main learning categories of language education: **communicative competencies, language proficiencies, cross-cultural experiences, and multiple literacies.**

These four categories are the most important matters to learn foreign languages.

Communicative competence refers to a learner's ability to use a language to communicate successfully. The aim of communicative language teaching and the communicative approach is communicative competence. In 1980 Canale and Swain defined it as composing competence in four areas:[2]

- Words and rules
- Appropriacy
- Cohesion and coherence
- Use of communication strategies

Communicative language teaching involves developing language proficiency through interactions arranged in meaningful contexts. This approach to teaching provides authentic opportunities for learning that go beyond repetition and

memorization of grammatical patterns in isolation. A central concept of the communicative approach to language teaching is communicative competence: the learner's ability to understand and use language appropriately to communicate in authentic (rather than simulated) social and school environments.

RESULTS

Language proficiency is a measurement of how well an individual has mastered a language. Proficiency is measured in terms of receptive and expressive language skills, syntax, vocabulary, semantics, and other areas that demonstrate language abilities. There are four stages which are gained step by step in language proficiency: novice, intermediate, advanced, superior. Language proficiency is measured for an individual by each language, such that the individual may be proficient in Uzbek and not proficient in another language:

DISCUSSION

Cross-cultural experience allows students of diverse cultural backgrounds to mix and learn from each other. The aim of this course is to provide students with the opportunity to obtain basic knowledge for understanding diversity and discover the excitement of cross-cultural communication, as a basis for future learning. Course students are offered the opportunity to not only understand cultural diversity by experiencing differences in ways of thinking and customs, but to participate in English and Uzbek mixed-language group discussions to acquire essential speaking, listening and reasoning skills and attitude required to communicate in a multi-cultural, multilingual setting. And there are ten strategies for effective Cross-cultural communication:

The term **multiple literacies** refers to our ability to interpret the many formats, sources, or media through which we obtain information. The four competencies that comprise multiple literacies are visual literacy, textual literacy, digital literacy, and technological literacy. Visual literacy refers to how we understand and interpret visual

representations of knowledge. Textual literacy refers to how we understand and interpret text. It also refers to our ability to communicate through written expression. Digital literacy refers to our ability to locate, evaluate, and synthesize digital sources (sources we find online). Technological literacy refers to our ability to use technology appropriately and responsibly.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion it should be emphasized that the significance of possessing linguodidactic knowledge is hard to overestimate. In order to take up learning a foreign language and to take professional decisions and make the right choice, he/she should have a clear idea of linguistic principles that compose those above mentioned categories, which regulate the process of a foreign language acquisition. These factors influence a learner's process, what regularities take place during the process of speech generation and how to use the resources of linguodidactic education. It can be stated that modern linguodidactics is an effective means of controlling the level of development of foreign language communicative competence, and as a result, serves as a tool for determining the quality of language education, monitoring the accuracy and completeness of the implementation of foreign language learning goals.

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